

Acetic acid is known to form four complexes with Cd(II).⁵ Formation of lesser number of complexes in case of halo-carboxylate ligands investigated may be attributed to their poor complex forming capacity. As Cd(II) is supposed to coordinate with four water molecules in aqueous solutions, the positions remaining short of those occupied by ligands may be supposed to be taken up by water molecules.

Filipovic⁵ *et al* have reported β_1 value (first step formation constant) of Cd-Acetate system as 20 from polarographic measurements. Thus the order of β_1 values of Cd II complexes of monobromo acetic, monoiodo acetic and acetic acid (A) is

The pK values^{6,7} of monobromo acetic, monoiodo-acetic and acetic acids which are 2.92, 3.19 and 4.76 respectively justify the above order of stabilities of complexes of these ligands.

References

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Gravimetric Determination of Mercury (II) with the ligand 1-imino-3-thioisindoline

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A NEW method for the gravimetric determination of Hg(II) using the sodium salt soln. of the above ligand¹ has been investigated. The above ligand has been used recently for the gravimetric determination of a number of metals by the authors²⁻⁴. Investigations have indicated that the ligand reacts with Hg²⁺ ions at pH ranging from 7.5 to 10 giving an orange red precipitate of mercury complex which is insoluble in most of the organic solvents. The element analysis of the complex shows that the mole ratio of the ligand to metal is 2 : 1.

All the reagents used were of AnalaR grade and the ligand was prepared by the method of Bagulev and Elvidge.

Element Analysis—Ligand	%C	%H	%N
Found	58.9	3.9	17.5
Required	59.3	3.7	17.3

The following stock solutions were prepared.

- (1) 1-Imino-3-Thioisindoline.....about 0.5% sodium salt soln. of the ligand of pH 7.5 to 10.
- (2) Mercuric Chloride.....Exact 1% soln. in water containing very small amount of HCl.

Determination of Mercury (II):

A known volume of 1 to 25 ml of soln. No. 2 was taken and diluted, to it a freshly filtered soln. No. 1 was added in excess (five to six times). An orange red precipitate of mercury complex was obtained, the precipitate was filtered after ten minutes through a medium porosity sintered glass crucible. It was washed with water several times and dried in a vacuum dessicator and weighed as Hg(C₈H₅N₂S)₂.

The gravimetric factor for Hg(II) is 0.3836.

Element Analysis—Hg(II)

Complex	%C	%H	%N
Found	36.4	1.8	10.8
Required	36.7	1.9	10.7

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF MERCURY (II) WITH THE LIGAND

Sl. No.	mg metal taken	mg metal recovered	% error
1	5	5.05	1.00
2	5	5.00	—
3	5	5.03	0.60
4	10	10.04	0.40
5	10	10.05	0.50
6	10	10.05	0.50
7	25	25.10	0.40
8	25	25.15	0.60
9	25	25.15	0.60

Interferences :

Most of the common anions do not interfere. Only few cations interfere these includes Cu(II), Ag(I), Cd(II), Au(III), Pb(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Tl(I).

Results and Discussion

The analytical data in Table 1, indicate that the ligand can be effectively used as a promising gravimetric reagent for mercury(II) in macro and semi-macro quantities. It is easy to filter the precipitate and bring the precipitate to constant weight within a period of half an hour.

The precision was fair, and the accuracy was generally within the permissible limits.

The concentration and temperature has no effect on precipitation. At pH < 6 a small amount of the water soluble form of the reagent may be precipitated and at pH > 10 a partial decomposition of the ligand is likely to take place.

References

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